

WETTING BEHAVIOR BETWEEN FIBRE & RESIN IN VACUUM ASSISTED RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING (VARTM)

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SUMMARY

The authors focus on wetting process of glass fibre-resin system in the vacuum assisted resin transfer moldings (VARTM). Effects of resin temperature and pressure difference driving the resin on the resin penetration process into the single-layered fibre bundles are experimentally investigated.

Keywords: VARTM, wetting, glass fibre, epoxy resin, fibre bundle

INTRODUCTION

Wetting in fibre bundle is a key phenomenon in composite material processing to control the dynamical features of the materials. Composite materials have been studied intensively around the world. Fibre reinforced plastics (FRP) of all is generally greater specific modulus and specific strength than metallic materials. Therefore, mainly two benefits (weight saving and performance improvement) are obtainable by using FRP in the industrial fields. Despite FRP brings larger cost than metallic materials, this material is one of potential solutions for social demands including reduction of CO₂ emissions, rising price for material and tightening of fuel efficiency requirements. The FRP has three problems to be solved; the first, reduction of production costs as stated previously, the second, improvement of productivity, and the third, dependability enhancement. Dependability of FRP is vigorously yielded by a control of wetting between fibre and resin. If the wetting is not good, voids occur at interface between the two, the locus of the polymer-fiber interactions, that proves most susceptible to failure. There should be no arguments on that the voids between the resin and the fibre would trigger unexpected and severe collapse of the products [1]. It is of great importance to understand and control the wetting as an interfacial thermal-fluid phenomenon [2]. Little knowledge has been accumulated, however, on this dynamic process of resin transfer in fibre bundles except the preceding works such as Ref. [3,4]. In the present study, the authors pay their special attention to wetting behavior between the resin and the fibre in the vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM).

Fig. 1 Wetting behavior (examples of (a) bad and (b) good wetting in water-steel system, and (c) uneven wetting between glass fibre and sizing agents).

EXPERIMENTS

Experimental Setup

Experimental apparatus consists of three major parts; molding part, resin supplying part, and observation part. In the molding part, the bundles of glass fibre of 25 μm in diameter are laterally aligned on the transparent glass plate. Peel cloth and mesh sheet are placed to cover the fibres. In the present system, inlet and outlet of the resin are drilled through the bottom plate, and the glass-top cover seals the whole system. The resin supplying part is illustrated in Fig. 2. The resin is sucked by vacuum pump through the molding part of the apparatus with a pressure difference ΔP between the mold and the resin bath. The reservoir of the resin is installed in a constant temperature bath, which enables the authors to supply the resin at designated temperature T_{resin} . The fiber-resin wetting behavior is captured by CCD cameras from above and beneath the fibre bundles simultaneously. Experimental materials are listed in Table 1.

Fig. 2 Experimental apparatus

Table 1 Experimental materials

Reinforcement	unidirectional glass knitted fabric	
	density	: 684 [g/m ³]
	stitching yarn	: polyester
	fibre density	: 0° insert : 7.0 [bundle/25 mm] : 90° insert : 2.0 [bundle/inch]
Matrix	epoxy resin	
	viscosity (at 25 [°C])	: 375 [mPa·s]
	specific gravity (at 25 [°C])	: 1.10

Analizing Procedure

Typical example of snapshot of the penetrated resin in the fibre bundle is presented in Fig. 3 (a); observed (right) from above (by CCD camera (1) in Fig. 2) and (left) from beneath (by CCD camera (2)) of the bundles. The resin travels from left to right in the both frames. Mainly three procedures are applied to detect the travelling edge of the resin front for further analysis. In the first procedure, difference image of each successive frame is obtained by subtracting background image. The background image is defined as an averaged frame from 10 frames detected in the concerned experimental run. In the second procedure, binary data is obtained from the brightness of the difference image by assuming a threshold above residual noise in the background image, as shown in Fig. 3 (b). Colored region corresponds to the detected resinous region, and

its boundary corresponds to the edge of the resin. Finally, in the third, each pixel in all successive binarized images is scanned to detect an instance when the variation of the brightness arises on that pixel as shown in Fig. 4. Figure 5 indicates a temporal variations of detected resinous area for top and bottom of the fibre bundle.

Fig. 3 Example of detected resinous area at the top of the bundle (left) and at the bottom (right). (a) original images and (b) binarized imaged (resinous: colored). Resin travels from left to right in both frames. $\Delta P = -65.0$ Pa, and $T_{\text{resin}} = 30$ °C.

Fig. 4 Example of detected time when the edge of the resin arrived at pixel concerned; at the top of fibre (left) and the bottom (right). Direction of the resin travel, and experimental conditions are the same as indicated in Fig. 3.

Fig. 5 Temporal variation of detected area of the resin penetration as shown in Fig. 4.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Detected arrival time of the resin front in the fibre bundles under various ΔP and T_{resin} is presented in Fig. 6. Significant difference of the resin penetration in the fibre bundles is clearly observed between the top and bottom views. At the top of the fibre bundles, the resin travels like almost plane wave, because the resin easily goes through in the mesh sheet placed above the fibre bundle. At the bottom of the bundle, on the other hand, the resin front exhibits a saw-edged shape; the resin comes through the peel cloth and the fibre bundles toward the bottom plate, and does prefer to travel between the bundles and the fibres due to the capillary force. The detected arrival time is quantitatively affected by ΔP and T_{resin} . The arrival time becomes shorter as the absolute value of the pressure difference $|\Delta P|$ becomes larger and/or the resin temperature T_{resin} becomes higher.

Figure 7 indicates the temporal variation of the detected resinous area at the top (left) and the bottom (right) of the fibre bundles as a function of the resin temperature T_{resin} under various pressure difference. It is clearly seen that the temporal variations of the resinous area are not qualitatively different between the top and the bottom of the bundles in spite of the significant difference of the penetrating resin front. And one can see a significant effect of the resin temperature on the resin penetration in the bundles. The viscosity of the resin negatively depends on the temperature; the higher the resin temperature, the lower the resin viscosity. This directly reflects the variation of the resin penetration into the bundle. In the following discussions, resin viscosity evaluated from the correlation given by the product company [5] is employed instead of the resin temperature to describe the resin penetration into the fibre bundles.

Fig. 6 Detected arrival time of the resin front at the top (left) and the bottom (right) of the fibre bundles; $(\Delta P [\text{kPa}], T_{\text{resin}} [^{\circ}\text{C}]) = (-65.9, 20)$ for the top pair, $(-96.1, 20)$ for the middle and $(-64.7, 50)$ for the bottom.

Fig. 7 Temporal variation of the detected resinous area at the top (left) and the bottom (right) of the fibre bundles as a function of the resin temperature T_{resin} under ΔP [kPa] = -67 (top), -80 (middle) and -96 (bottom).

Mean growth rate of the detected resinous area is plotted in Fig. 8. This growth rate is defined by a slope between the points at 10 % and 90 % of the whole detected resinous area under each condition as shown in Fig. 7. One can clearly see the same trends of the mean growth rate in quality between the top and bottom surfaces of the bundles. Figure 9 indicates growth rate of penetrated resinous area, obtained by subtracting the mean growth rate of the detected resinous area at the bottom of the bundles from that at the top. In the case of the single-layer fibre bundles, the growth rate of the penetrated

resinous area corresponds qualitatively to those at the top and/or bottom of the bundles. The authors will carry out further research on the effect of the resin penetration into the multi-layered bundles.

Fig. 8 Mean growth rate of resinous area at the top of fibre (left) and bottom (right). Resin viscosity is evaluated by a formula in the sentence.

Fig. 9 Growth rate of penetrated resinous area into the fibre bundles.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The authors focus on wetting process of glass fibre-resin system in the vacuum assisted resin transfer moldings (VARTM). Effects of resin temperature and pressure difference driving the resin on the resin penetration process into the single-layered fibre bundles are experimentally investigated. The penetrated resinous region is evaluated by simultaneous observation of the resin traveling at the top and bottom the bundles. It is

found that the growth rate of the penetrated resinous region can be well predicted by the growth rates of the resin traveling at either top or bottom of the bundles.

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